

Supplementary Material

**Experimental and Modeling Study of the Nanofiltration of Alcohol-
Based Molecules and Amino Acids by Commercial Membranes**

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Figure S1

Fig. S1 - NaCl rejection as a function of the permeate flux and ethylene glycol feed concentrations for the Desal 5DK membrane. NaCl feed concentration was $0.5 g L^{-1}$.

Figure S2

Fig. S2 - NaCl rejection as a function of permeate flux and glycine feed concentrations for MPF-34 and Desal 5DK membranes. NaCl feed concentration was 0.5 g L⁻¹.